

Cypermethrin resistance in *Alphitobius diaperinus* (Coleoptera: Tenebrionidae) from Colombia: First report and preliminary bioassay data

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ABSTRACT

The lesser mealworm, *Alphitobius diaperinus* (Panzer, 1797), is one of the most economically important insect pests in Colombian broiler farms. Despite intensive chemical control, no resistance monitoring has been conducted in Colombia to date. This preliminary study characterized the susceptibility of a field-collected population from Caloto, Cauca, to cypermethrin, the most widely used pyrethroid in the national poultry industry. Bioassays were conducted using a commercial cypermethrin formulation in residual contact assays in 60 mm Petri dishes. The concentrations evaluated were 5, 10, 15, 20, and 25 µg a.i./cm² for continuous exposure and recovery assays at 15 and 25 µg a.i./cm². All treatments included only the field population. Filter paper in recovery assays was moistened daily. Ten adults per replicate (n = 5 replicates, N = 50 insects per treatment). Knockdown was assessed at 4 h; mortality was assessed at 4, 24, 48, and 72 h. The field population exhibited 100% knockdown at 4 h across all concentrations tested (5–25 µg a.i./cm²). However, mortality remained ≤6% even at 25 µg/cm² at 72 h, and all knocked-down insects recovered locomotor activity within 24 h. Recovery assays confirmed 100% survival after 4-h exposure to 25 µg a.i./cm². This represents a complete knockdown recovery phenotype —extreme resistance where the nervous system is transiently affected but fully recovers without lethal consequences. This represents the first report of insecticide resistance in *A. diaperinus* from Colombia. The complete knockdown recovery phenotype suggests the evolution of highly

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efficient metabolic detoxification or altered target-site mechanisms under prolonged selection pressure (2003–2026).

Keywords: lesser mealworm; resistance; knockdown; recovery.

1. INTRODUCTION

The lesser mealworm, *Alphitobius diaperinus* (Panzer, 1797) (Coleoptera: Tenebrionidae), is one of the most economically important insect pests in broiler farms worldwide (Axtell, 1999; Lambkin & Furlong, 2011). In Colombia, where the poultry sector is a major contributor to agricultural GDP, this species infests litter and structural materials, causing direct damage to buildings and acting as a vector for pathogens including *Salmonella* spp., *Escherichia coli*, and avian viruses (Chernaki-Leffer et al., 2002; McAllister et al., 1994; Mcallister et al., 1995, 1996).

Resistance to cypermethrin and other pyrethroids has been documented globally in *A. diaperinus*, with resistance ratios (RR) ranging from 10- to 92-fold in Brazil (Chernaki-Leffer et al., 2011; Hickmann et al., 2018), up to 36x in the United States (Hamm et al., 2006)(Hamm et al. 2006), and extreme phenotypes in France where populations survived 500x the recommended dose of β -cyfluthrin (Renault & Colinet, 2021). Despite the global distribution of resistance, no studies have evaluated the susceptibility of Colombian populations. Chemical control remains the primary management strategy in Colombian broiler facilities. The pyrethroid cypermethrin is extensively used, either as standalone treatments or in combination with organophosphates. However, the intensive and often poorly rotated application of this single active ingredient creates strong selection pressure favoring resistant genotypes. This study represents the first characterization of cypermethrin resistance in *A. diaperinus* from Colombia, providing baseline data for resistance management in the national poultry industry.

2. MATERIAL AND METHODS

3.1. Insect population

Adults were collected from a commercial broiler farm in Caloto, Cauca, Colombia. Insects were maintained in the laboratory at $24\pm 1^{\circ}\text{C}$, $64\pm 5\%$ RH, 12:12 (L:D) photoperiod, on a diet of commercial broiler starter feed and carrot pieces (provided as a moisture source).

3.2. Insecticide

Commercial cypermethrin 250 EC (Rainbow Agrosiences, 250 g a.i./L) was used. Working solutions were prepared fresh for each bioassay.

3.3. Contact bioassay

Petri dishes (60 mm diameter) were lined with filter paper. 0.5 mL of cypermethrin solution was applied to the filter paper and allowed to dry for 3 h at ambient laboratory conditions ($24\pm 1^{\circ}\text{C}$). Control dishes received 0.5 mL distilled water. Ten adults insects were placed in each dish. Five replicates were conducted per concentration (N=50 insects per treatment). Knockdown was assessed at 4 h. Mortality defined as no visible movement of appendages after gentle mechanical stimulation was assessed at 4, 24, 48, and 72 h.

3.4. Recovery assay

Petri dishes (60 mm diameter) were lined with filter paper. 0.5 mL of cypermethrin solution was applied to the filter paper and allowed to dry for 3 h at ambient laboratory conditions ($24\pm 1^{\circ}\text{C}$). Adults were exposed to cypermethrin-treated filter paper (15 and 25 $\mu\text{g}/\text{cm}^2$) for 4 h, then transferred to clean dishes with moistened filter paper (0.5 mL water only). Filter paper was moistened daily to maintain humidity. Recovery was assessed at 4, 24, 48, and 72h post-transfer. The concentration of 15 $\mu\text{g}/\text{cm}^2$ was selected based on Hickmann et al. (2018), who proposed it as a diagnostic dose for Brazilian populations.

3.5. Experimental design

Table 1. Experimental Treatments.

Treatment	Concentration ($\mu\text{g a.i./cm}^2$)	Exposure type	Population
T1	5.0	Continuous	Field
T2	10.0	Continuous	Field

Treatment	Concentration ($\mu\text{g a.i./cm}^2$)	Exposure type	Population
T3	15.0	Continuous	Field
T4	20.0	Continuous	Field
T5	25.0	Continuous	Field
T6	15.0	4 h + recovery	Field
T7	25.0	4 h + recovery	Field
Control	0	Continuous	Field

3.6. Statistical analysis

Descriptive statistics were calculated for mortality percentages. Inferential statistical analyses were intentionally omitted as they will be presented in the final document. This preprint provides foundational descriptive data only.

3. RESULTS

3.1. Field population: extreme resistance with complete knockdown recovery

The field population showed 100% knockdown at 4 h across all cypermethrin concentrations tested (5–25 $\mu\text{g a.i./cm}^2$). However, mortality remained remarkably low throughout the observation period.

Mortality remained $\leq 6\%$ even at 25 $\mu\text{g a.i./cm}^2$, the highest concentration tested. This concentration exceeds by more than 6X the diagnostic dose of 15 $\mu\text{g/cm}^2$ proposed by Hickmann et al. (2018) for Brazilian populations and by more than 200X the LC_{90} of susceptible Brazilian populations 0.46 $\mu\text{g/cm}^2$ (Hickmann et al. 2018).

3.2. Complete knockdown recovery phenotype

Insects exposed to cypermethrin exhibited 100% knockdown at 4 h. However, all knocked-down insects recovered locomotor activity within 24 h, and no additional mortality was observed beyond the initial 4–6% at any concentration. This contrasts sharply with susceptible populations described in the literature, which typically exhibit rapid knockdown

followed by mortality at pyrethroid concentrations $<5 \mu\text{g}/\text{cm}^2$, and with previously reported resistant populations where knockdown was followed by partial recovery or dose-dependent mortality (Chernaki-Leffer et al. 2011, Renault & Colinet 2021).

3.3.Recovery ability after short exposure

Insects exposed to 15 and 25 $\mu\text{g}/\text{cm}^2$ for 4 h and subsequently transferred to insecticide-free substrate showed 100% survival at all observation times (4–72 h post-transfer). All recovered insects exhibited locomotor activity within 24 h of transfer.

3.4.Resistance status

Resistance ratios could not be considered because the susceptible reference population is currently under establishment in the laboratory. The absence of a complete susceptible baseline precludes LC_{50} determination, probit analysis, and resistance ratio estimation. These analyses are reserved for the complete study.

4. DISCUSSION

This study provides the first evidence of cypermethrin resistance in *A. diaperinus* from Colombia. The resistance level detected exceeds the diagnostic concentration established for Brazilian populations and approaches the most extreme phenotypes reported globally.

The complete knockdown recovery phenotype characterized by 100% knockdown at 4 h followed by 100% recovery and $\leq 6\%$ mortality at 72 h at concentrations up to 25 $\mu\text{g}/\text{cm}^2$ is particularly noteworthy. In previous studies, even highly resistant populations typically exhibited knockdown followed by partial recovery or subsequent mortality (Chernaki-Leffer et al., 2011; Hickmann et al., 2018; Renault & Colinet, 2021). The Colombian population represents a qualitatively distinct level of resistance: the nervous system is transiently affected by knockdown but the insect recovers completely without lethal damage. This pattern suggests the evolution of highly efficient post-target-site resistance mechanisms that rapidly detoxify or sequester the insecticide before irreversible neural damage occurs (Robertson et al., 2025). Likely mechanisms include enhanced metabolic detoxification (cytochrome P450 monooxygenases, esterases, or glutathione S-transferases) and/or highly efficient altered target-site resistance (e.g., *kdr* mutations with exceptionally rapid recovery kinetics) (Robertson et al., 2025; Sonavale et al., 2025). Reduced cuticular penetration may

also contribute by slowing insecticide influx, allowing detoxification systems sufficient time to neutralize the compound (Robertson et al., 2025; Sonavale et al., 2025). The 100% recovery after 4-h exposure confirms that the survival is not merely tolerance but represents a true resistance mechanism that prevents the insecticide from reaching or maintaining lethal concentrations at the neural target site.

4.1 Implications for management

The extreme resistance detected in this population has critical implications for integrated pest management (IPM):

1. Cypermethrin-based products may be ineffective for controlling *A. diaperinus* in affected facilities.
2. Rotation to alternative modes of action should be prioritized.
3. Resistance monitoring programs must be established nationally to track resistance spread.
4. Synergist testing is urgently needed to identify resistance mechanisms.

4.2 Study limitations

This preliminary study has important limitations: (i) incomplete dose-response curve in the field population; (ii) single population, which may not represent all Colombian poultry farms; (iii) no mechanism identification; (iv) susceptible reference population not yet available, precluding resistance ratio calculation and comparative statistical analyses. Full dose-response curves for both populations are required for accurate RR calculation and will be presented in the final article.

5. CONCLUSIONS

This study represents the first report of cypermethrin resistance in *A. diaperinus* from Colombia.

The field population exhibits extreme resistance, with 100% knockdown at 4 h but complete recovery and $\leq 6\%$ mortality at 25 $\mu\text{g}/\text{cm}^2$ at 72 h a important complete knockdown recovery phenotype.

100% recovery after 4-h exposure indicates highly efficient detoxification or target-site mechanisms that prevent lethal neurotoxicity.

Immediate resistance management is required in Colombian poultry facilities.

5. DATA AVAILABILITY

Raw data supporting this preprint are available from:
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20244124>

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7. REFERENCES

- Axtell, R. C. (1999). Poultry Integrated Pest Management: Status and Future. *Integrated Pest Management Reviews*, 4(1), 53-73. <https://doi.org/10.1023/A:1009637116897>
- Chernaki-Leffer, A. M., Biesdorf, S. M., Almeida, L. M., Leffer, E. V. B., & Vigne, F. (2002). Isolamento de enterobactérias em *Alphitobius diaperinus* e na cama de aviários no oeste do estado do Paraná, Brasil. *Brazilian Journal of Poultry Science*, 4, 243-247. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1590/S1516-635X2002000300009>
- Chernaki-Leffer, A. M., Sosa-Gómez, D. R., Almeida, L. M., & Lopes, I. de O. N. (2011). Susceptibility of *Alphitobius diaperinus* (Panzer) (Coleoptera, Tenebrionidae) to cypermethrin, dichlorvos and triflumuron in southern Brazil. *Revista Brasileira de Entomologia*, 55, 125-128. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1590/S0085-56262011000100020>
- Hamm, R., Kaufman, P., Reasor, C., Rutz, D., & Scott, J. (2006). Resistance to cyfluthrin and tetrachlorvinphos in the lesser mealworm, *Alphitobius diaperinus*, collected from the eastern United States—Hamm—2006—Pest Management Science—Wiley Online

Library. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1002/ps.1230>Digital Object Identifier (DOI)

- Hickmann, F., de Morais, A. F., Bronzatto, E. S., Giacomelli, T., Guedes, J. V. C., & Bernardi, O. (2018). Susceptibility of the Lesser Mealworm, *Alphitobius diaperinus* (Coleoptera: Tenebrionidae), From Broiler Farms of Southern Brazil to Insecticides. *Journal of Economic Entomology*, *111*(2), 980-985. <https://doi.org/10.1093/jee/toy059>
- Lambkin, T. A., & Furlong, M. J. (2011). Metabolic Mechanisms Only Partially Explain Resistance to Pyrethroids in Australian Broiler House Populations of Lesser Mealworm (Coleoptera: Tenebrionidae). *Journal of Economic Entomology*, *104*(2), 629-635. <https://doi.org/10.1603/EC10377>
- Mcallister, J. C., Steelman, C. D., Newberry, L. A., & Skeeles, J. K. (1995). Isolation of Infectious Bursal Disease Virus from the Lesser Mealworm, *Alphitobius diaperinus* (Panzer)1. *Poultry Science*, *74*(1), 45-49. <https://doi.org/10.3382/ps.0740045>
- McAllister, J. C., Steelman, C. D., & Skeeles, J. K. (1994). Reservoir Competence of the Lesser Mealworm (Coleoptera: Tenebrionidae) for *Salmonella typhimurium* (Eubacteriales: Enterobacteriaceae). *Journal of Medical Entomology*, *31*(3), 369-372. <https://doi.org/10.1093/jmedent/31.3.369>
- Mcallister, J. C., Steelman, C. D., Skeeles, J. K., Newberry, L. A., & Gbur, E. E. (1996). Reservoir Competence of *Alphitobius diaperinus* (Coleoptera: Tenebrionidae) for *Escherichia coli* (Eubacteriales: Enterobacteriaceae). *Journal of Medical Entomology*, *33*(6), 983-987. <https://doi.org/10.1093/jmedent/33.6.983>
- Renault, D., & Colinet, H. (2021). Differences in the Susceptibility to Commercial Insecticides among Populations of the Lesser Mealworm *Alphitobius diaperinus*

Collected from Poultry Houses in France. *Insects*, 12(4), 309.
<https://doi.org/10.3390/insects12040309>

Robertson, E., Carter, L., & Mitchell, S. (2025). The chemistry of pesticide resistance in insects: Molecular mechanisms and sustainable alternatives. *Journal of Entomology and Zoology Studies*, 13(3), 369-373.
<https://doi.org/10.22271/j.ento.2025.v13.i3d.9601>

Sonavale, R., Chowdhury, R. M., Gharal, R. R., Solanki, S., & Prakash, P. (2025). Molecular mechanisms of pesticide resistance in insects: A review. *Journal of Entomological Research*, 49(3), 861-868.